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Corona Virus (Covid-19) And Its Impact On Educational System In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The sudden outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) which originated from the city of Wuhan, China, has become a major public health challenge for not only China but, also countries all over the world. Infact, the pandemic has led to the total lockdown of most of the human activities in various parts of the world. The World Health Organization announced that the outbreaks of the novel coronavirus have constituted a public health, emergency of international concern as of February 26, 2020, Covid-19 has been recognized in 34 countries, with a total of confirmed cases of 4.9 million at least 188 countries with 323,300 deaths and nearly 1.7 million recoveries as at 2014 of May 2020. Infection control measures are necessary to prevent the virus from further spread and to help control the epidemic situation. There is a double that the interference of the coronavirus pandemic has caused so many challenges in the Nigerian education system in the line this, this paper reveals the concepts of coronavirus (COVID – 19). Issues, challenges and the impact on the sustainable development of the educational system of Nigeria.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Nigerian Educational System.

INTRODUCTION

On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) announced that this outbreak had constituted a public health emergency of international concern (Mahase 2020). The novel coronavirus was initially named 2019 in corm and officially as severe acute respiratory symptom coronavirus 2 (SARS COV-2). As of February 26, Covid-19 has been recognized in 34 countries, with a total of 80,239 laboratory – countries cases and 2,900 deaths (WHO, 2020).

As of April 21st, 2020, approximately 1,703 billions learners have been affected with the sudden closures of school in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. According to UNESCO monitoring, as of the date

above 191 countries have implemented nationwide closures and 5 have implemented local closures, impacting about 98.4 percent of the world's student population. On 23 March, 2020, Cambridge International Examination (CIE) released a state announcing the cancellation of Cambridge IGCSE, Cambridge O level, Cambridge international As and A level, Cambridge AICE Diploma, and Cambridge pre-u examination for the May/June 2020 set across all countries. International Baccalaureate exams were cancelled.

Efforts to curtail the spread of COVID-19 through non mineral interventions and preventive such as social-distancing and self-isolation have prompted the widespread closure of primary, secondary and tertiary schooling in over 100 countries. Nigeria as a country have as well ensured all schools and personal experience a compulsory stay at home order so as the prevent further spread of this deadly virus from spreading among students and school personal since it an easily be contacted through direct contact with the carrier of the virus. In fact many unified examinations have to be suspended.

Most of Africa's 54 conditions are and with confirmed cases and death, tells due to COVID-19, some have closed their borders and banned international flights, local and international trade are declining at a drastic rate. The Democratic Republic of the Congo, Romanta, Bouth Africa, Tunisia, Nigeria and most of the African countries have declared complete lockdowns. According to Woodwosen, Tompat and Daimen (2020), research on the April 2020 African economic revealer that African could experience economy loss of between USS9 billions and US&200 in 2020, with the GDP shrinking by eight points. In South Africa, growth is expected to contrast by 1.5% in the first two months outbreaks, due to its effect on key economic sectors, such as mining and tourism. Ethiopia's recent request for assistance, on behalf of the Affrication nations to the G20 forum, for USS150 which emergency financing, the freezing of interest rates on bound and the cancellation of debts is a clear indication of the massive threat to the continent's economics and sustainable development.

Mathematics modeling has shown that towns mission of an outbreak may be stepped shown by solving of schools which are the major atmosphere to social governing. However, effectiveness of this were depends on the contacts and social distancing principles children maintain outside then schools. School closure helps a lot when it is introduced at the early stays, but if it records late to an outbreak, it may be less effective and try not to book any impact at all because by then the disease could have going out of hurts in the school system. There is why over the years education sector have remain a sensitive part of the sustainable developments of any country, because the rune in the development of any country is majorly declared by the educational sectors. Again in some case where necessities are not properly manager. The reopening of schools after a paramedic closure may, result in increased infection rates, in fact doubled the until figure. The closures as a result of the paramedic does not only affect the educational sector, it has also led to the suspension of all public gathering, closure of major markets, religious organizations were restricted from worshipping together and may other gatherings, activities were on held during the laying period. Even with all these, it is difficult to measure the specific impact of school closures, because it varies from place to place, persons to persons, the impact may be possible or effective on individuals as the case may be. Nevertheless, this research will examine the noticeable effects of Covid-19 on the education system of Nigeria.

PANDEMIC AND CLOSURE OF SCHOOLS

They trying period of 1918 – 1919 influence paramedic in the United States School closures and public governing trans were introduced with the helps in the resolution of mortality rates. It was record that cities that implement such interventions earlier had greater delays in reading peace peak mortality rates. Schools were closed for four weeks according to a study of 43 us cities' response to the Spanish flu. School closures were shown to reduce mortivility from the Asian flu by 90% during the 1959-58 outbreak and up to 50% in controlling influeuza in the us, 2004 – 2008, Miilie 2007 all NI flu paramedic. The closure of schools in the city of Oitu in Japan helped in the successful decrease in the number of infected students even at the peak of infection. Mandating School closures and other social distancing measures were associated with a 292 to 37% reduction in influenza transpiration rates. Early closures of schools in

the United State delayed the peak of the 2009 HINI flu pandemic. Despite the overall success of closing schools, some starching of school closure concluded that it is not the best measure in the control of pandemic and that they process is ineffective. For example a study conducted in Mirchigan found that “district legal reactive school closures were in effective.

In the year 2009 when there was an outcomes of since flu in the United Kingdom, in an article Titled “closure of schools during an influences pandemic” published in the lanset infections dismeal, a group of epidemidogists enclosed the closure of schools in order the reduce further spread of the infection, and buy time to research and produce effective vaccine. They studied previous influenza pandemic including the 1918 flue pandemic, the influenza pandemic of 1957 and the 1968 flu pandemic, they reported the effect of school closure would have particularly with a large percentage of doctors and nurses being women of whom half had children under the school going eye of 16. They as well looked at the past trays of the spread of influenza in france during French school holidays and noted that cases of the reduced when these was closure of schools. Looking at when teachers in Isreal went on structure during the flu of 1997 – 2000, visits to doctors and the members of respiratory infections dropped in seldom.

Many countries have rightly decided to close schools, colleges and university. The crisis crystalizes the dileam policy measures are facing between closing schools (reducing contact and serving lives) and keeping them open allowing workers to work and maintaining the schooling. The severe short-term disruption if felt by many families around the world; home schooling is not only a massive shield to parents’ productivity, but also to children’s social life and learning. Teaching is moving online, on unerrupted and unprecedented scale, student assessments and also living online with a lot of error and uncertainty for everyone. Many assessment have simply been cancelled, importantly, these intemption will not just be a short-term issues but can also have long-term consequences for the affected cohorts and are lively to increase inequality.

Unlike Western countries, the Federal Ministry of Education’s School – closure directive did not produce policy measures on how to ease learning distruptions for children and how to address the digital mean of learning which may be alternative methods to physical teaching and learning process in the dynamic society. In an account of Taibat, the coordinated education response to COVID-19 pandemic on the landing page of the Ministry website is vague and does little to address the leaving needs of the most valuable and disadvantaged. The single wells documented response is the Nigeria Education in emergency working group (NEEWG) strategy published on 9 April 2020, which aims to mitigate the negative imput of the school closure on learners and teachers in north-east Nigeria. While the efforts of the Federal and State Government in health sector and in providing financial stimulus packages and emergency palliantropist hust be commended, ignoring the education sector would be disastrous. As emphasized by UNESCO, temporary school closure comes with high social and economic cost, with severs impact on children from disadvantaged background impacts of COVID-19 on the Nigeria” Education System.

In Nigeria, the outbreaks of lassa fever, lives fins, mockery pox, ebola disease and others didn’t weight down the socio-economic and educational system as of the case a coronavirus this has been raising dust in the country, educational system and heartfelt burden to the concern personal, knowing well the possible effects of the prolong holiday as a result of the pandemic.

IMPACTS ON EDUCATION: SCHOOLS

Going to school is the best public policy tool available to develop skills and potentials, school time can be fun, and front an economic point of view. The primary point of being in school is that it increases a child’s ability to become a useful and acceptable member of the society. Even a relatively short time in school has a long imput in the life of a child: a short period of missed school may have consequences for skill growth in future. This is why we cannot estimate how much the COVID-19 interruption will effect festering; it is on the visible effect we can sea, the gradual decay of inbuilt abilities may not be easily noticed very precisely. We are now in a new world far different from the things we use to know. The school time tables and scheduled have changes. Infact at the resumption of the school after the lockdown.

So, many grounds needs to be covered in orieafor the educational system of Nigeria to be able to complete with the world's educational system. Facilities in schools are been under utilized during lockdown, some might have damaged as a result of not been used for a long period of time.

IMPACT ON EDUCATION: GRADUATES AND SCHOOL LEARNERS

There is no doubt that students in terminal classes in lower and higher leaves of education system of Nigeria has been hell on spot; they were unable to or even more to the next level on their academic pursuit this had be to the set a great back of the smooth running of educational sector of Nigeria and the world at large. What makes education beautiful and fulfilling is the progress in terms of moving to the work level, graduating and becoming a useful and acceptable members of the society after being exposed to the teaching – learning processes in the school.

Evidence suggest that poor manner conditions at and can be workers to accept lower paid jobs for survival first and this has permanent effects on the careers of some graduate because they have been doing the jobs for related to their area of specialization for so many years which on the long run has made them not been fulfilled in their choice earners. Oreopondous et al (2011) show that graduates from programmes with high predicted learning, can compensate for their poor starting point through both within and across-term rearing gins, but graduate from other programme have been found to experience permanent earing losses from graduating in a recession.

Ada (2024) consequences of COVID-19 pandemic to Nigeria

- Closure of Universities
- Loss of lives
- Alteration of academic calendar
- Penalty to all students
- Disruption of academic programmes
- Quarantilling of individual.

CONCLUSION

The outbreak of coronavirus has shaken the educational sector of Nigeria of its strategy. In fact, looking at the end of the pandemic. It could be something we are going to live with for a long period of kins. There is no doubt that there is going to be a serious set-back in the development of Nigeria education system if the coronavirus pandemic lockdown is not properly managed by the government and concern personnel. Schools calendar has been dumped, there is economic development of the country, which has affected the education finance as well. Since the family income depends on the economic growth of any country, most of the families in Nigeria are experiencing economic hardship as a result of the pandemic lockdown. Some of the vulnerable families having their children under the Federal Government feeding (COFO) being faced with the challenge of going in search of food for their children while they are with them at home. Unfortunately, the illiteracy level of some parents in Nigeria is not helping the matter because not every parents or guidance could handle the black and white teaching of their children. This on a long run will cause children in these academic endeavours in fact many of them may from there drop of school and take source other things.

The pandemic lockdown has led to the shortage of funds for the educational system. Parents as well as been fixed with the reality of having to pay extra cost on their children academic whenever they resume to school. This is certainly trying time for the economy.

A hit on the sustainable development of the county and it is not going to be an easy experience for some households who could baselly afford daily balanced diet who have been for them to become a useful and acceptable number of the society. It work be surprising if a larger percentage of students dropped out of schools after the pandemic lockdown in Nigeria as a result to parents to been the cost of financing their children education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Since it was observed that there were no proper plans in place to curb and manage the influence of coronavirus on the educational system. It is highly recommended for the government and concerned educational personal to ensure there are futuristic plans in case of another similar experience. This is Covid-19, nobody knows what other occurrences will happen in future and will lead to intemption of activities of educational system of Nigeria, therefore, plan are to be created for future effective education. Having observed that even the E-learning chosen as the alternatives to be used in reaching out to the learned in the period of lockdown has not successful world because of non unemployment of expert to manage the ICT section of the Nigeria education system, huge tainf charges front various network providers in Nigeria.

Government should help create an enabling environment devoid of environment hazards. Government should come up with policies that will eradicate diseases in the country.

Preventive measures to avert COVID-19 pandemic are as follows:

1. Government should be up and doing in providing safe environment devoid of hazards and accidents.
2. Government should enforce measures that will mitigate diseases and ensure individual disease free.
3. Individually should keep to Government order by reciprocating to check up and attending to hospitals.
4. Individuals should keep off from certain things that could jeopardize environmental safety.

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